
Deliverable D4.2

Report on dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement – v1

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Terms and abbreviations

CMM	Capability Maturity Model
CMS	Content Management System
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CPT	CONCEPTIVITY SARL
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
KPI	Key exploitable results
MTRL	Market Technology Readiness Level
POLIMI	POLITECNICO DI MILANO
R&I	Research and Innovation
SW	Software
SWForum.eu	European forum of the software research community
TECNALIA	FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION
TRUST-IT	TRUST-IT SRL
UOXF	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD
UX	User experience
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The paramount objective of SWForum.eu is to raise awareness and strengthen the competitiveness of the European Software Industry by facilitating a sustainable European forum for stakeholders representing scientific researchers, providers, developers, operators and policy-makers relevant to software technologies, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity.

Now at M18, the SWForum.eu project has identified and started to deliver a set of project assets related to this. These are promoted and disseminated through work package (WP) 4. These assets are:

- ❏ European Software Project Observatory offers a comprehensive view of research and innovation initiatives, focussing on ICT-50-2020 “Software Technologies”, by ensuring engagement across software-related domains and vertical sectors across the EU and Associated Countries.
- ❏ The Market & Technology Readiness Level (MTRL) framework aims to provide decision-makers with a holistic view of a project’s maturity in a simple way - with a single score. It offers decision-makers a faster way to assess, measure and support software technology projects.
- ❏ Cross fertilisation workshops bring together stakeholders coming from different communities and expertise, such as the industry and the academia, as well as policymakers, closing the gap between research and industry.

This document provides information on the activities carried out in the first reporting period (M1-18), their impact, and proposes a set of actions for the future.

The document provides information on how the project has targeted the main target stakeholders through various channels such as the swforum.eu website, social media, workshops, webinars and other R&I events. The document also reports on quantitative and qualitative measures demonstrating the impact of the project.

The first part of this document overviews the impact of the activities together with the technical work packages (WPs). The second part is specifically centred on the communication and dissemination efforts deployed in WP4.

Section 2 – Focuses on the overall community impact of SWForum.eu, spanning innovations and results on its technical assets.

Section 3 – Reports on the impacts of the community building through different communication channels

Section 4 – Covers the strategy for impact assessment for communication and dissemination activities for the upcoming months.

Section 5 – Presents a set of exploitable online services intended to promote long-term sustainability of SWForum.eu beyond the duration of the project.

ANNEX I – Timeline of activities from M19 – M30.

ANNEX II – List of SWForum.eu organised and participating events.

1 Introduction and scope of the document

This document provides an overview of the implementation of the plan described in [1] up until M18 and how the project has responded to review recommendations provided in M12. In particular, the document will focus on how the consortium has communicated and disseminated to specific stakeholders. The deliverable also provides a set of next steps for the coming months (M19-30).

1.1 Background and related deliverables

WP4 Communication, dissemination and MTRL has a horizontal role in the SWForum.eu project with regards to communicating project objectives and disseminating results to target stakeholders. All deliverables are, therefore, relevant and must be shared and linked to WP4 activities. Moreover, those contributions will be the source of content for the website and social media activities of the project.

In particular, the following deliverables (also submitted between M1-M13) are closely related to [1].

Table 1: Related deliverables

Deliverable	Title	WP	Lead	Submission Date
D2.1	Cross-fertilization workshop report - v1	2	POLIMI	Aug 2021
D2.4	Project Radar Taxonomies	2	UOXF	Mar 2021
D2.5	Project Radar Technical Roadmap	2	UOXF	Jun 2021
D2.6	Project Radar landscape analysis - v1	2	UOXF	Dec 2021
D3.1	Landscape Reports - v1	3	CPT	Jun 2021
D3.3	Software Forum Research Roadmap - v1	3	TECNALIA	Oct 2021
D3.6	Fellowship programme, governance structure and business model for SWForum.eu - v1	3	POLIMI	Dec 2020
D3.7	Fellowship programme, governance structure and business model for SWForum.eu - v2	3	POLIMI	Dec 2021
D4.4	MTRL methodology and assessments - v1	4	UOXF	Dec 2021

1.2 Main achievements from M1-M18

In [1] the team outlined the plan for the project's communications, defined on the different stakeholders relevant to SWForum.eu. Below, we give a summary of the main goals and objectives for this strategy and analyse our actions and their impacts up to M18.

This document is part of the collaborative effort of all partners, maximising and boosting synergy and uptake with the software research community that addresses ICT-50-2020 as a Coordination

and support action (CSA). Partners' contributions include cooperation with the consortium partners, and establishing a working relationship with peer EC-funded projects organisations and multipliers relevant to software technologies, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity.

In the first 18 months of this initiative, despite the significant impact of the worldwide pandemic that also affected the project's effort to a certain extent, some foundational outcomes have been achieved:

- ❑ SWForum.eu managed to build a widely acknowledged personalised project branding and visual identity that made the project recognisable among the European software community.
- ❑ A seamless and broad community of stakeholders (better detailed in Section 3) that encompasses influential research actors and organisations within the European context.
- ❑ A populated social media channel that plays a key role in the junction between the project, end-users and overall community, and constitutes a source of shared insights, newsworthy items, organised SWForum.eu events and other software technology, digital infrastructure and cybersecurity-related events.
- ❑ The creation of a fully-fledged, continuously improved website as the heart of its communication strategy to showcase the main features of the projects, as well as a safe repository of documents and deliverables.

Strategy for Stakeholder Engagement

- ❑ Profiling the SWForum.eu community in terms of the stakeholder groups, tracking community development impacts, including participants to SWForum.eu cross-fertilisation workshops, webinars and other events (see [2] and [3]).
- ❑ Identifying the most relevant venues for stakeholder engagement, such as 3rd-party events, as well as hosting SWForum.eu webinars and workshops.
- ❑ Promoting event participation, roles and networking opportunities for physical events.
- ❑ Reporting on event outcomes, takeaways and impacts. This includes the keynote presentations from each speaker and the call for papers' presenters.
- ❑ Ensuring regular community interaction through professional networks like LinkedIn and social media channels like Twitter.

Strategy for communication

- ❑ Implementing the communication strategy defined in [1], which defines a set of KPIs against which impacts are monitored.
- ❑ Adapting the plan as necessary to reflect project developments and in the face of situations such as the COVID-19 pandemic with the virtual event organisation.
- ❑ Intensifying other forms of engagement, such as project hub recruitment, webinars, videos, newsletters to ensure the community keeps abreast of developments and new opportunities, working closely with the synergies established.
- ❑ Populating the SWForum.eu website and measuring impacts automatically generated through a dedicated dashboard.
- ❑ Measuring overall impacts of the communications strategy.

The project is now moving to its principal phase, where the creation and consequent exploitation of more tangible results and assets are expected, where assets can be shared (products, services, technologies), lessons learned, and policies developed and facilitating engagement in the development of a set of research and innovation roadmaps for the future of software technologies.

In the attempt to attain such objectives, the SWForum.eu team will keep joining forces and establishing synergies with the relevant initiatives, EC-funded R&I projects and organisations to make the project's outcomes as available as possible and to reach out to the widest audience within the research, academia, scientific and policy arena.

The deliverable is to be considered as a living document that could evolve following the advancements and needs of the other Work Packages, most of all those directly involved in the elaboration of the project's technical assets (namely WP2 and WP3). Furthermore, the overall unfolding of the COVID-19 situation might steer the direction of the communication in different directions, as better indicated in the concluding part of the document (Section 5).

2 SWForum.eu community building: Stakeholder engagement up to M18

The current COVID-19 situation has disrupted the delivery of physical events and participation at events since the start of the project. One of the key pillars of SWForum.eu is an outreach programme to the relevant EC-funded project specifically with the ICT-50-2020 “Software Technologies” projects to foster synergy by helping them in promoting their project, results and any latest updates. Moreover, the team has been continuously engaged to strengthen synergies and collaboration through different channels which are detailed in the following sections.

2.1 Cross-fertilisation workshops

Cross fertilisation workshops are one of the key assets of the SWForum.eu, aiming to promote EU cross-fertilisation between the areas of software, digital infrastructures, and cybersecurity. These events foster discussions to gather input and feedback from the whole software community.

SWForum.eu has delivered three cross-fertilisation workshops in the first 18 months of its lifetime. The workshops have been an essential element of the SWForum.eu project, bringing together stakeholders coming from academia and industry representing different domain and application sectors. As foreseen in the Grant Agreement, there are two types of cross-fertilisation workshops: public and private.

Public Cross-Fertilisation Workshops

These workshops are intended as outreach events to the broad public. Two of these workshops have been held in this reporting period, and the results are described in [2].

First SWForum.eu Workshop on Trustworthy Software and Open Source¹ Date: 23-25 March 2021, Online

Audiences Reached:

71% live attendees out of 86 registered participants coming from 23 countries around the world.

Onboarding strategy

- Sent personalised email invitations to EC-funded projects within the software community, 3rd party media networks, and consortium partners
- Created a social media promotional campaign
- Opened a LinkedIn event page
- Created a dedicated page on the SWForum.eu website
- Designed a branding image such as the save the date, event banner and social media banners.

Figure 1: First SWForum.eu Cross-fertilisation Workshop banners

¹ <https://swforum.eu/events/first-swforum.eu-workshop-trustworthy-software-and-open-source>

❏ **Second Workshop: Research Challenges, Collaboration, and Coordination in European Software Engineering Projects²**

Date: 29 June – 1 July 2021, Online

Audiences Reached:

59% live attendees out of 29 registered participants from 10 EC-funded projects.

Onboarding strategy

- ❏ This event was by invitation only to the EC-funded R&I projects within the software community.
- ❏ Partners sent a personalised email invitation to the identified R&I projects.
- ❏ Create a social media promotional campaign
- ❏ Create a dedicated event page on the SWForum.eu website.

Figure 2: Second SWForum.eu Cross-fertilisation Workshop banners

To offer a quantitative idea of the broad impact such outreach actions have, below we present an analysis of participants as of geographical coverage and stakeholder groups. Participants come from 25 countries: 20 EU Member States (EU20) and 5 Non-EU/global. For EU20, Italy and Spain are by far the most represented countries, followed by the Netherlands, Germany, Greece and the United Kingdom.

Figure 3: Participants in the first two public SWForum.eu Cross-fertilisation Workshops

² <https://swforum.eu/events/second-swforum.eu-workshop>

Private Cross-Fertilisation Workshops

These workshops not open to the public; rather, they are invitation-only to a selected group in order to collectively elaborate strategic directions for SWForum.eu and for the European research community at large. There has been one such workshop held in this reporting period

First SWforum.eu Sustainability Workshop

Date: 24 January 2022, Online

Invited participants included representatives from the funded projects, from the European Commission, and from the EU research community. An full and exhaustive report of the results of this important cross-fertilisation is provided in [4].

Next Steps

Currently the Consortium is preparing information for the participants in the Sustainability Workshop of January 2022, in order to gather feedback and commence planning for the next steps for the establishment of a strategic community around SWForum.eu preparing recommendations for the road ahead in the European software engineering community to present to representatives of the Commission.

2.2 MTRL Webinars

The Market & Technology Readiness Level (“MTRL”) framework aims to provide decision-makers with a holistic view of a project’s maturity in a simple way - with a single score. It offers decision-makers a faster way to assess, measure and support software technology projects.

The MTRL webinars aim to provide detailed guidance through the definition of a methodological approach to the improvement of a project’s MTRL, Mentoring, Technology Transfer & Best Practices, with an eye also toward EU policy innovation. Further details on the MTRL methodology and assessments can be found in [3].

SWForum.eu has organised two of the series of four webinars on the MTRL framework, analysing a software technology project's maturity in a holistic, straightforward fashion, providing management with a simple yet powerful decision-making tool.

SWForum.eu Webinar: Market & Technology Readiness Levels³

Date, Location: 26 May 2021, Online

Goal: Provided an overview of MTRL analysis and grading, achieving a single-valued result, and guidance for software technology projects embarking on their MTRL self-assessment journey.

³ <https://swforum.eu/events/swforumeu-webinar-market-technology-readiness-levels>

Understanding criteria for optimal self-assessment of project outcomes using Market Technology Readiness Levels⁴

Date, Location: 27 October 2021, Online

Goal: Discussed the assessment process in detail and showcased the aims of the nine (9) different questions that are asked during the self-assessment process. Detailed interpretations of answers to these questions for different contributors within the software ecosystem and equivalences made between different sectors who are all active and using the MTRL assessment process.

These webinars gathered almost representatives of 20 EC-funded projects, shown in Figure 4, that are invited to submit their MTRL self-assessment questionnaire⁵.

Figure 4: MTRL Webinars participants

Next Steps

In the next period, we plan to deliver the scheduled webinars at appropriate intervals. The set of MTRL webinar series will be offered to guide software engineering projects through their MTRL self-assessment journey.

⁴ <https://swforum.eu/events/understanding-criteria-optimal-self-assessment-project-outcomes-using-market-and-technology>

⁵ https://swforum.eu/sites/default/files/MTRL/MTRL%20Questionnaire_V2.xlsx

On top of the four MTRL webinar series is the SWForum.eu webinars which will invite related R&I projects to contribute to webinars where they showcase their best practices, or they can offer mentoring or technology transfer best practices, and allow them to present their results.

The consortium will be organising a dedicated call to invite the projects focusing on topics according to those identified in [5].

3 Communication channels evolution and impact

Communication is key to the success of SWForum.eu. The SWForum.eu website is the central communication and dissemination channel of the project. The other main communications channels are social media, videos, newsletter and events. All other channels contribute to pointing stakeholders towards the website.

The SWForum.eu website (<https://www.swforum.eu/>) is powered by a professional CMS (Drupal) and has a modern look and an intuitive structure. Menus and submenus are designed to improve the user experience and facilitate navigation through the whole website, as shown in Figure 5.

Over the first 18 months of the project there has been an evolution and progression in these communication channels.

3.1 Website

The SWForum.eu website underwent a significant transformation in M7. A complete redesign was made, along with the addition of two important components in the Online Forum and the Project Hub.

The redesign was performed by the experienced COMMpla team, starting from the mockups and looking to fulfil the user requirements with an effective user experience (UX) design. The new website was implemented on Drupal 8.

The home page is much more impactful with a video slider showing a video custom-made for the website. Further down users are introduced to the main features of the website, the forum and the project hub (See Section 5.2, as well as the project radar (See Section 5.3) yet to be implemented. They are then encouraged to sign up to the website and become a part of the SWForum.eu community.

Figure 5: Structure of the SWForum.eu Website

3.2 Social media

SWForum.eu is using two key social networks, Twitter and LinkedIn, first of all, to build its community and ultimately to communicate all the outputs and results. Both communities have been growing steadily.

3.2.1 Twitter

SWForum.eu’s Twitter has been steadily growing. Since M3 when D4.1 was published, it has gained 178 followers, coming to a total of 246. In the same time , a total of 119 Tweets have been sent, having been seen 92.910 times (impressions), leading to 9972 profile visits and 84 mentions. SWForum.eu has gained some important followers who are aggregators such as the technology media page @TechNative which has 87.4K followers.

Figure 6: A recent mention by a relevant software-related H2020 project

As a CSA, one of SWForum.eu’s roles is to support the projects funded under the ICT-16-2018 call. A strategy was implemented on Twitter to retweet at least one of these projects per working day. This has been a successful way to promote these projects and their results, as well as increase their engagement with SWForum.eu.

3.2.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn will be mainly used to onboard new relevant stakeholders and invite these stakeholders to relevant events and webinars. It is particularly useful because you can search for people with LinkedIn is being mainly used to onboard new relevant stakeholders and invite these stakeholders to relevant events and webinars. It is particularly useful because of the capability to search for people with the specific job type in the specific geographic area that makes them part of a specific stakeholder group. Through connecting with these individuals, they can be invited to events and see relevant updates through the company page.

At the moment of writing, SWForum.eu’s LinkedIn account has 862 followers, well surpassing the KPI set at the beginning of the project of 500 followers. Of these followers, the four biggest industries represented are Information Technology and Services (371 followers), Computer Software (101 followers), Research (56 Followers) and Higher Education (53 followers).

3.3 Videos and Podcasts

The SWForum.eu videos section includes a series of video interviews with the consortium, the MTRL Webinars, as well as the recordings of the first two SWForum.eu workshops. All videos are hosted on YouTube. SWForum.eu’s videos have a total of 403 views at the time of writing.

Figure 7: Videos on SWForum.eu

The videos section also gives the possibility to projects which are part of the project Hub to add their own videos and promote them through the SWForum.eu website. This adds value for projects taking part in SWForum.eu. So far two projects have made use of this opportunity.

So far SWForum.eu has produced one podcast introducing the project. Another three podcasts are planned before the end of the project to cover some key outputs of the project, MTRL, Project Radar, and the European Research Roadmaps.

3.4 Newsletter and publications

In March 2021, the first newsletter was released featuring the first SWForum.eu cross-fertilisation workshop, and two other releases promoting the SWForum.eu events. SWForum.eu has issued seven special announcements, supporting the organised events during year 1. These are distributed to a database of more than 100 individuals who have all signed up to receive this.

This has led to the following results, which helps the SWForum.eu project to reach a wider array of stakeholders and increase engagement in the EU ICT ecosystem, especially in the promotion of the SWForum.eu organised events mentioned in sections 2.1 and 2.2.

Table 2: Newsletter performance

Newsletter	3 newsletter releases, 7 special announcements
Subscribers	142 subscribers
Number of recipients	825 recipients (total within 7 issues)
Open rate	39.3% with a total of 324 opened
Click rate	11.8% with a total of 97 clicked
Click-to-open rate	29.9% (as of 8 Mar 2022)

Note: The average email open rate should be between 15-25%. The average click-through rate should be about 2.5%. Your average click-to-open rate should be between 20-30%

The newsletter is published and sent every six months to keep stakeholders informed on recent updates related to the project, upcoming events, highlights from the previous events and getting insights from the EU ICT and software community and experts.

Figure 8: SWForum.eu Newsletter issues

Articles and event news. The publication of regular news pieces on the website aims to ensure regular interactions with the software community, allowing stakeholders to be continuously up to date with the project's progress and developments. At the moment of writing, SWForum.eu has published a total of 63 articles and event news, 18 of which were published by the project mini-site representatives, garnering an average of 36 views per content.

The WP4 team will continue to engage with the related projects and encourage them to utilise their respective project mini-sites, which will allow them to have extra visibility to promote their results, reports, videos and other dissemination materials, and upcoming events to reach a wider array of stakeholders through the SWForum.eu platforms.

Publishing of reports. Public deliverables are published by the authors or by SWForum.eu on Zenodo. The SWForum.eu Zenodo community⁶ will house all the public reports and publications created by the team, making them available to the general public, especially the “Research & Innovation Roadmap Reports” and “Recommendations and Vision papers”.

Figure 9: News, Events and Zenodo community

3.5 Events

Events are where the SWForum.eu project can maximise impact on its stakeholders. WP4 promotes and supports the organisation and the dissemination of every coordination meeting, workshop, webinars and conference that SWForum.eu is attending. As mentioned in section 2, this area has been greatly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has extended over most of the project lifespan covered by this deliverable. An “Event Tracker” has been set up in a Google Sheets file shared by the Consortium to systematically track the principal ICT-related events in Europe, and to gather meaningful takeaways from the consortium members that participated in any such events.

SWForum.eu has organised four of its own events: two (2) cross-fertilisation workshops and two webinars (section 2), and supported one virtual event, which was organised by the European Commission in collaboration with H-CLOUD, HUB4CLOUD, EU-IoT. Moreover, consortium members attended nine (9) third party events from M1-M18 at national, European and international levels. The complete list of events can be found in Annex II.

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/communities/swforum>

The main output from the organised SWForum.eu events include:

- ❏ A first engagement with other H2020 Projects, engaging also with several experts in the field and 25 projects to register and manage their project mini-site in the Project Hub.
- ❏ Reaching out to other projects to introduce the MTRL methodology for the software project assessment.
- ❏ Gathering together projects for insightful suggestions on how to improve the online forum both in its functionality and use.

Out of the many events, we highlight the outcomes and impacts of selected events:

❏ **Europe's Digital Decade: Empowered by Open Source⁷**

Figure 10: SWForum.eu participated in the OFE event

On 5 November 2020, SWForum.eu participated in the OpenForum Europe online event on «Europe's Digital Decade: Empowered by Open Source.»

A major takeaway from this event is that open source is all about community and collaboration. This is true at all levels, from the individual up through governmental institutions. This means that we must all be willing to get involved and contribute.

❏ **Sharing the latest opportunities for Software and System Reuse at ICSR Tunisia 2020⁸**

Figure 11: SWForum.eu presented in the ICSR Tunisia 2020

John Favaro, a Senior Analyst from Trust-IT Services and SWForum.eu communications head, played an active role in the panel session on 3 December 2020 entitled "Opportunities for reuse and opportunistic reuse practices: Trends and Challenges⁹", tracing the history of systematic reuse back to the beginnings of the discipline, and highlighting the latest opportunities for reuse due to the rise of open source and open data, topics that are being studied and promoted by SWForum.eu.

⁷ <https://swforum.eu/events/europes-digital-decade-empowered-open-source-openforum-europe>

⁸ <https://swforum.eu/events/sharing-latest-opportunities-software-and-system-reuse-icsr-tunisia-2020>

⁹ https://whova.com/embedded/session/icsr_202011/1333334/?view=

 EC Virtual Event “Digital Autonomy in the Computing Continuum”¹⁰

Figure 12: SWForum.eu presented in the EC virtual event

This event was organised by the European Commission in collaboration with H-CLOUD, HUB4CLOUD, EU-IoT. Leire Orue-Echevarria (project coordinator) and Luis Busquets Pérez (EC Programme Officer, Cloud and Software Unit) have participated in the panel discussion session on “Open Source for Digital Autonomy” together with key experts in the field. This session has addressed the role of open-source software and hardware in a Computing Continuum that will support Europe’s digital autonomy, in alignment with Thomas Skordas’ comments at the ICT directors’ meeting on 07 October 2021.

These events provided visibility to the CSA project within the EU ICT ecosystem. Events have been identified for their timelines with respect to SWForum.eu outputs, topics and audience relevance. Participation spans virtual and physical presentations, panel debates, workshops and tutorials for focused and effective communication, dissemination and engagement outcomes, with live reporting via Twitter, updates and LinkedIn posts.

Further steps

Further steps beyond M18 include two initiatives in current planning, which involve participation in third-party events. The first initiative is the participation of SWForum.eu and the funded projects under its umbrella in ESOC 2022 (9th European Conference On Service-Oriented And Cloud Computing) from 22-24 March 2022. Specifically, SWForum.eu and a selection of these funded projects presented current research in the Projects Track of the conference.

A second initiative currently underway is the organisation of a satellite workshop (live in presence or alternatively hybrid/virtual) to CAISE 2022 (34th International Conference on Advanced Information Systems Engineering), in Leuven, Belgium, from 06-10 June 2022. This is an ongoing initiative with workshop content and structure in a definition phase.

3.6 SWForum.eu community

WP4 focuses on building the SWForum.eu engaged stakeholder community including contacts coming from the website, event participation, and newsletter subscribers. The SWForum.eu stakeholder engagement strategy is KPI-based with additional qualitative metrics aimed at analysing the community in more detail, such as geographical and industry distribution.

The table below reflects the status of the stakeholder KPIs at M18 (as of 08 March 2022). From the table below, in comparison to the last reporting (M3).

Table 3: KPI Status for Digital Community Interaction

SWForum.eu Stakeholder Metric	Status	
	M3	M18
Database contacts	19	157
Event participants	0	170

¹⁰ <https://swforum.eu/events/ec-virtual-event-digital-autonomy-computing-continuum>

Twitter Followers	48	250
LinkedIn Followers	66	899

As of the reporting period, there are almost 40 EC-funded projects that engaged with the team through organised SWForum.eu events and the Project Hub. The complete list is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: EC-funded Project Synergy

Project Name	Project Name
AI4PublicPolicy	Automated, Transparent Citizen-Centric Public Policy Making based on Trusted Artificial Intelligence
AI-SPRINT	Artificial Intelligence in Secure PRivacy-preserving computing coNTinuum
ARTICONF	smart social media eCOsystem in a blockchain Federated environment
BLUE-CLOUD	Blue-Cloud: Piloting innovative services for Marine Research & the Blue Economy
CHARITY	Cloud for Holography and Cross Reality
CloudButton	Serverless Data Analytics Platform
COSMOS	DevOps for Complex Cyber-physical Systems
CyberSec4Europe	Cyber Security for Europe
Cyberwatching.eu	The European watch on cybersecurity privacy
DataCloud	ENABLING BIG DATA PIPELINE LIFECYCLE ON THE COMPUTING CONTINUUM
DECENTER	Decentralised technologies for orchestrated cloud-to-edge intelligence
DECODER	Developer Companion for Documented and annotated code Reference
De-RISC	De-RISC: Dependable Real-time Infrastructure for Safety-critical Computer
EnergyShield	Integrated Cybersecurity Solution for the Vulnerability Assessment, Monitoring and Protection of Critical Energy Infrastructures
EOSC-SYNERGY	European Open Science Cloud - Expanding Capacities by building Capabilities
EXPANDS	EOSC Photon and Neutron Data Services
FAIR4Health	Improving Health Research in EU through FAIR Data
FASTEN	Fine-Grained Analysis of Software Ecosystems as Networks
FOCETA	FOUNDATIONS FOR CONTINUOUS ENGINEERING OF TRUSTWORTHY AUTONOMY
GN4-3N	Horizon 2020: H2020-SGA-INFRA-GEANT-2018 Topic [b] Increase of Long-Term Backbone Capacity
HUB4CLOUD	The European Cloud Computing Hub to grow a sustainable and comprehensive ecosystem
InterQ	Interlinked Process, Product and Data Quality framework for Zero-Defect Manufacturing
IoTAC	Security by design IoT development and certificate framework with front-end access control

MEDINA	Security framework to achieve a continuous audit-based certification in compliance with the EU-wide cloud security certification scheme
MORPHEMIC	Modelling and Orchestrating heterogeneous Resources and Polymorphic applications for Holistic Execution and adaptation of Models In the Cloud
NGI Ledger GeneCosent	Next Generation Internet Ledger
ONTOCHAIN	Trusted, traceable and transparent ontological knowledge on blockchain
OpenAIRE	OpenAIRE
PHYSICS	Optimized hybrid space-time service continuum in FAAS
PIACERE	Programming trustworthy Infrastructure As Code in a sEcuRE framework
Policy Cloud	Policy Management through technologies across the complete data lifecycle on cloud environment
RADON	Rational decomposition and orchestration for serverless computing
ReachOut	The Beta Testing Campaign Platform for Research Project
SERRANO	TRANSPARENT APPLICATION DEPLOYMENT IN A SECURE, ACCELERATED AND COGNITIVE CLOUD CONTINUUM
SODALITE	Software Defined Application Infrastructures management and Engineering
SWForum.eu	European forum of the software research community
UNICORE	A Common Code Base and Toolkit for Deployment of Applications to Secure and Reliable Virtual Execution Environments
VeriDevOps	VeriDevOps
XANDAR	X-by-Construction Design framework for Engineering Autonomous & Distributed Real-time Embedded Software Systems

While the majority of the SWForum.eu database contacts community come from European countries (23), there are some software advocates from other non-European countries, Asia (4), Africa (2), America (2) and Oceania (1).

The largest participation is from Spain (56), followed by Italy (47), the Netherlands (35), Germany (25) and the United Kingdom (21). 30% of the community members are female.

The majority of the interested stakeholders are from R&I projects with a 33% (distribution count) followed by R&I projects and Tech SMEs/Start-ups.

Figure 13: SWForum.eu Community – geographical (left) and stakeholder group (right)

4 Monitoring activities and measuring impacts for M19-M30

It is fundamental to monitor and measure the impact of all the communication activities carried out by the SWForum.eu team in line with the commitment to deliver a structured communication strategy. For continuous and easy monitoring for the communication and dissemination, the WP4 team has set up a shared dashboard (for internal usage), collecting and visually rendering relevant data from the SWForum.eu website, social media channels and online activities. Necessary adjustments will be made during the project.

The SWForum.eu dashboard was set up by collecting data through Google Analytics and rendering it through Google Data Studio. The Dashboard is a customised analytical tool created for SWForum.eu that generates real-time information on a core set of metrics and Key Performance Indicators. The dashboard is interactive and contains multiple filtering functions so that the internal team having access to it can easily access specific and time-limited data and set up communications strategies accordingly. Data currently displayed on the dashboard includes:

- ❏ Website data: page views, sessions, users, users' countries, page views and sessions in time, website sessions according to countries, website users' source, most visited pages and average time spent on the page;
- ❏ Twitter data: followers count, tweets count, retweets, likes, specific data related to each tweet;
- ❏ LinkedIn data: followers, impressions, likes, engagement and specific data related to each post.

At the time of writing, the website registers the following scores in comparison to M12: 1.5K users (with 28.6% improvement), 2.4K sessions (28% improvement), 14.3 pageviews (28.7% improvement), and 43.55% bounce rate (with 10.1% improvement).

Figure 14: Website performance M1-M18 (as of 8 March 2022)

5 Exploitable services for long-term sustainability

Given the objective of SWForum.eu to ensure its sustainability beyond the conclusion of the project, a set of online services have been designed in the first half of the project and are being progressively elaborated over the course of the project as new use cases appear and new data becomes available from the ecosystem of European area research projects.

The exploitability of these services will depend on the ability of the project to build a community around each of them sufficient to become self-sustaining through a general perceived utility. There is precedent for successful sustainability in previous projects (e.g., Cyberwatching.eu) with similar services, providing some directional guidance to the project for orienting the online services toward particular groups. The first set of target stakeholders is the funded research projects for the Mini-Hub and Radar services, whereas top-level individual researchers are the initial target stakeholders for the online forum service, due to a perception that this group will provide the most initial impact and impetus toward community growth.

5.1 Online discussion forum in software technologies

One of the main features of the SWForum.eu platform is an online forum where users can discuss issues related to software, cybersecurity and digital infrastructure. This forum was not foreseen within the original Grant Agreement. However, the risk management procedures invoked by the consortium with the arrival of the COVID-19 crisis led to the conclusion that community building measures originally intended to be carried out through face-to-face meetings, workshops, conferences, and the like, must be migrated to online mechanisms and measures. The decision was made to introduce an online discussion forum, based upon previous work of partner Trust-IT, in the form of its **Forum+** facilities.

Figure 15: Post in the Forum

The Forum+ software was analysed by the consortium for suitability for the goals of the SWForum.eu project, and it was determined that investment in the development of new functionalities not yet present in the facility was needed. External funds originally intended for the face-to-face measures were re-allocated to strengthen the Forum+ User Experience and to introduce more robust definition and handling of discussion topics. These measures were accompanied by a gradual re-orientation by the consortium of its community-building strategy toward support for the emergence of online discussion communities around a flexible set of topics relevant to current research both in the funded projects and in the broader EU research community. Currently, users can post discussions to message boards under specific topics, reply to other discussions and follow discussions, thereby receiving email notifications for any comments on the discussion thread.

The WP4 team have also implemented a strategy for engagement on the forum that involves creating blogs on relevant topics, outlining a challenge and presenting a question for discussion, linking to a discussion thread where readers can reply with their insights. The first blog posts were made in March 2022 after the first set of updates to the Forum+ software was made.

A second round of new technical developments in the Forum+ facilities is currently planned, oriented at the creation of facilities for creating closed / **moderated discussion groups** on the platform. This use case emerged from the Sustainability Workshop held in January 2022, when it was proposed that the top-level European researchers participating in that workshop be able to use the Forum+ facilities for their work in elaborating recommendations to policymakers on the future of software technologies in Europe. In order to carry out this work, the researchers needed to be able to guarantee an environment in which a restricted, agreed group of participants worked together and only published public outputs when the group agreed that the outputs of their work were in a suitable form. These new technical developments will involve the re-allocation of some external costs and are expected to be in place within two months.

5.2 Project Hub

At the start of the project, the SWForum.eu team has created the hub of project mini-sites, the “SWForum.eu Project Hub¹¹”, whose ultimate objective is to constitute a complete, unabridged and updated compilation of EU-funded research projects on software topics. This initial list consists of the ICT-50-2020 “Software Technologies” projects.

Table 5: ICT-50-2020 Projects

Project Name	Project Name
COSMOS	DevOps for Complex Cyber-physical Systems
ELEGANT	Secure and Seamless Edge-to-Cloud Analytics
FOCETA	FOUNDATIONS FOR CONTINUOUS ENGINEERING OF TRUSTWORTHY AUTONOMY
PIACERE	Programming trustworthy Infrastructure As Code in a sEcuRE framework
VeriDevOps	VeriDevOps
XANDAR	X-by-Construction Design framework for Engineering Autonomous & Distributed Real-time Embedded Software Systems
SWForum.eu	European forum of the software research community
CLASS	Edge and Cloud Computation: A Highly Distributed Software for Big Data Analytics
SOLIDATE	SOftware Defined AppLIcation Infrastructures management and Engineering

The list of projects has evolved as part of the onboarding strategy of the SWForum.eu, adding several EC-funded projects that were identified through public information available through CORDIS¹².

Projects are listed alphabetically on the Project Hub landing page as shown in the figure below. This includes the project name, logo, link to their hub entry and link to their website. Entries can be filtered according to keywords, project domain and sector.

¹¹ <https://swforum.eu/project-hub>

¹² <https://cordis.europa.eu/>

Figure 16: Project Hub page and project mini-sites

This includes the project name, logo, link to their project entry and link to their website. Initially, each project has its page where a general description, logo and website address is included. Information on target stakeholders and end-user benefits is also included by SWForum.eu partners when this information is identifiable from publicly-available information. Content for the Project pages either comes from information provided by the project (e.g., through the onboarding campaign or call) or by desktop research by the SWForum.eu partners based on publicly-available information (e.g., project website and or project factsheet on CORDIS).

SWForum.eu has implemented a specific communication and engagement strategy to onboard projects using the following mechanisms:

- Desktop research – As a first step, initiatives have been gathered together through an exercise of desktop research by consortium partners. This has involved engagement with EC official channels for the EC-funded initiatives.
- Email invitations – A series of targeted email messages have been sent out to relevant contacts promoting the Project Hub, and inviting initiatives to join the software project hub and create their profiles. Data collection and content creation of hub entries based on publicly available information on projects.

The benefit of being part of the project hub is mainly free visibility for projects in this unique, software technology focused online reference. In addition, we enhance this by also providing free visibility to projects through the website homepage, invitation to events and promotion through social media. This is described below with examples.

- Project Spotlight - Having a dedicated web page in the Project Hub, where projects will be extensively promoted as one of the featured projects of the week.

This includes a dedicated page on the Project Spotlight¹³ page, a news piece featuring the key assets and results offered by the project and promotion on the SWForum.eu social media channels.

Figure 17: Project Spotlight

During the M1-18, several projects we contracted to be featured on the Project Spotlight programme. However, most of them do not feel confident with their latest results as their project is just in the initial stage of technological development.

- Social media promotion - Support dissemination and communication activities through SWForum.eu social media channels (Twitter¹⁴ and LinkedIn¹⁵). With dedicated resources on this, we already have a solid base of over almost 1000 followers.

Figure 18: Tweet promoting project on the social media channels

¹³ <https://swforum.eu/project-hub/project-spotlight>

¹⁴ <https://twitter.com/SWforumEU>

¹⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/swforumeu/>

- ▣ Visibility at events - Publish news and events coming from the project on the SWForum.eu website as their extra channel for visibility. Participate at various workshops organised by SWForum.eu to encourage clustering, collaboration and promoting project outputs. This includes the cross-fertilisation workshop¹⁶ organised for all projects in the software research unit.

Next Steps

With a clear procedure in terms of identifying and publishing projects in the project hub now established in M1-18, this will continue in the coming months.

New EC-funded projects that started in 2021 and that will start in 2022 will be identified and contacted for either SWForum.eu to create a simple overview of the project, or for them to provide a more updated project overview with the latest results of their project.

The team will invite again the earlier project that has started in 2020 and Q1-Q2 2021 to be part of the Project Spotlight programme, allowing them to showcase their latest results and develop assets to the multistakeholder community of the SWForum.eu.

5.3 Project Radar

Another key exploitable result of the project is the Project Radar, which works in tandem with the Project Hub described earlier. The status of the project radar is described in [6], to which the reader is referred for details.

¹⁶ <https://swforum.eu/events/swforum-events>

6 References

- [1] SWForum Consortium, "SWForum.eu Deliverable D4.1 "Plan for dissemination, communication & stakeholder engagement" (M3)," 2020.
- [2] SWForum Consortium, "SWForum.eu Deliverable D2.1 "Cross-fertilization workshop report - v1" (M11)," 2021.
- [3] SWForum Consortium, "SWForum.eu Deliverable D4.4 "MTRL methodology and assessments - v1" (M15)," 2022.
- [4] SWForum Consortium, "SWForum.eu Deliverable D3.7 "Fellowship programme, governance structure and business model for SWForum.eu - v2" (M15)," 2022.
- [5] SWForum Consortium, "SWForum.eu Deliverable D3.3 "Software Forum Research Roadmap - v1" (M13)," 2021.
- [6] SWForum Consortium, "SWForum.eu Deliverable D2.6 "Project Radar landscape analysis - v1" (M15)," 2021.

7 Conclusion

The COVID-19 epidemic extending over the greater part of the duration of SWForum.eu to date created a necessity for considerable risk management activities in the area of communications and community building, with the result that the project - like so many others in the community - was constrained to pivot toward outreach primarily in the virtual space.

At the same time, however, it provided an opportunity for the consortium to undertake a thorough review and revision of its outreach and community-building strategy. The successful Sustainability Workshop held shortly before the M18 milestone, with the participation of a significant portion of the most influential actors in the current European software engineering research community, was a particularly important factor in a re-orientation of the project strategy toward focusing community building activities on a renewed and robust online facility for interaction among these experts. This redirection of the project strategy promises to produce an even greater impact than the original strategy may have produced, together with a more realistic path toward sustainability of the SWForum.eu concept.

In the coming months, we will be working toward the realisation of this new community building strategy together with the rest of our consortium partners and collaborators within the community of funded projects.

ANNEX I – Timeline of activities (M19-M30)

The below timeline reflects the upcoming activities, deliverables and potentially participated events in the coming months. In June 2022, the team is preparing their participation in the CAISE 2022.

Figure 19: SWForum.eu overall communications timeline

ANNEX II – List of events

As Table 6 shows, at the time of writing there is a single event planned that is directly organised by SWForum.eu – the cross-fertilization workshop and webinars (see Section 2). There are several upcoming events that are happening in the coming months that the team is considering to participate, see Table 7.

Table 6: Events (M1-M18) – organised and participated events

Events	Date, Location	Category	Typology
First SWForum.eu Workshop on Trustworthy Software and Open Source	23-25 Mar 2021, Online	SWForum.eu organised event	Workshop
FIWARE Cybersecurity Day	13 May 2021, Online	3 rd -party event	Conference
SWForum.eu Webinar: Market & Technology Readiness Levels	26 May 2021, Online	SWForum.eu organised event	Webinar

Second SWForum.eu Workshop: Research Challenges, Collaboration, and Coordination in European Software Engineering Projects	29 Jun – 1 Jul 2021, Online	SWForum.eu organised event	Workshop
3rd International Workshop on Cyber-Security Threats, Trust and Privacy Management in Software-defined and Virtualized Infrastructures (SecSoft)	2 Jul 2021, Online	3 rd -party event	Workshop
Shaping the future of cybersecurity - Priorities, challenges and funding opportunities for a more resilient Europe	13 Jul 2021, Online	3 rd -party event	Conference
Understanding criteria for optimal self-assessment of project outcomes using Market and Technology Readiness Levels	27 Oct 2021, Online	SWForum.eu organised event	Webinar
EC Virtual Event “Digital Autonomy in the Computing Continuum”	11 Nov 2021, Online	3 rd -party event	Conference
OFA Symposium 2021: The European Commission Open Source Study	16 Nov 2021, Online	3 rd -party event	Conference
The EU Open Source Policy Summit	4 Feb 2022, Online	3 rd -party event	Conference

Table 7: Upcoming Events in the software and open source domain

Name	Start Date	End Date	Location	Organiser
ICICIT	25/03/2022	26/03/2022	Madrid, Spain	World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology
ICST	04/04/2022	14/04/2022	Virtual	IEEE
OSMSES	04/04/2022	05/04/2022	Aachen, Germany	IEEE
ICSCISIT	08/04/2022	09/04/2022	Athens, Greece	World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology

NOMS 2022	25/04/2022	29/04/2022	Budapest, Hungary	IEEE
Linux App Summit	29/04/2022	30/04/2022	Rovereto, Italy	KDE & GNOME
ICITSE	03/05/2022	04/05/2022	Rome, Italy	World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology
BotSE	09/05/2022	09/05/2022	Virtual	IEEE
IBM Think	10/05/2022	11/05/2022	Hybrid	IBM
CAIN'22	16/05/2022	17/05/2022	Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania USA	IEEE
EnCyCriS	16/05/2022	16/05/2022	Virtual	IEEE
SERP4IoT	19/05/2022	19/05/2022	Virtual	IEEE
ICSE	25/05/2022	27/05/2022	Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania USA	IEEE
COMSCI	30/05/2022	02/06/2022	Virtual	IEEE
openSUSE Conference	02/06/2022	04/06/2022	Nuremberg, Germany	OpenSUSE
CAiSE 2022	06/06/2022	10/06/2022	Leuven, Belgium	KU Leuven and Ghent University
ISDFA	06/06/2022	07/06/2022	Hybrid/Istanbul, Turkey	IEEE
OW2Con	08/06/2022	09/06/2022	Paris, France	OW2
openSUSE Summit at OSCAL	18/06/2022	19/06/2022	Tirana, Albania	OpenSUSE
MPSoC	19/06/2022	24/06/2022	Megève, France	IEEE
COMPSAC	27/06/2022	01/07/2022	Turin, Italy	IEEE
NetSoft	27/06/2022	01/07/2022	Milan, Italy	IEEE
QSW	10/07/2022	16/07/2022	Barcelona, Spain	IEEE
FOSS4G 2022	22/08/2022	28/08/2022	Firenze, Italy	OsGEO
FedCSIS	04/09/2022	07/09/2022	Sofia, Bulgaria	IEEE
Open Source Summit Europe	13/09/2022	16/09/2022	Hybrid/Dublin, Ireland	Linux Foundation
ESEM	22/09/2022	23/09/2022	Helsinki, Finland	IEEE
SoftCOM	22/09/2022	24/09/2022	Split, Croatia	IEEE
ICSME	3/10/2022	7/10/2022	Limassol, Cyprus	IEEE
VISSOFT	3/10/2022	4/10/2022	Limassol, Cyprus	IEEE
IWSC	8/10/2022	8/10/2022	Limassol, Cyprus	IEEE
EMSOFT	10/10/2022	14/10/2022	Virtual	IEEE

ICSTCC	19/10/2022	21/10/2022	Sinaia, Romania	IEEE
SST	19/10/2022	21/10/2022	Osijek, Croatia	IEEE
IEEE 8th World Forum on Internet of Things	3/11/2022	18/11/2022	Hybrid/Yokohama, Japan	IEEE
DevConf.cz	01/2023	01/2023	Virtual	Red Hat
The EU Open Source Policy Summit	02/2023	02/2023	Virtual	OpenForum Europe & Linux Foundation
FOSDEM	02/2023	02/2023	Virtual	Fosdem
CloudFest 2023	03/2023	03/2023	Europa Park, Germany	CLOUDFEST
Cloud Expo Europe	03/2023	03/2023	London, UK	Closerstill